

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 764632

AGEISM IN THE MEDIA

Online Webinar - April 26th 13.00 UK TIME

@ITNEuroAgeism <https://euroageism.eu/>

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Welcome to 'Ageism in the Media webinar

- Please ensure you have signed in using your full name rather than a nickname
- Please note that all participants' microphones will be mute
- We encourage you to ask questions during this session, which should be done using the Chat and will discuss then during the breakout rooms
- Please remember that everything you type may be visible to all others who join the session, so we do advise you not to share personal data
- Please note this session will be recorded
- Life Transcript

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Ageism and active contribution to society

- Employers-employees
- Late working life trajectories
- Welfare sustainability

Towards an age-friendly society

- Digital technologies
- Equality legislation

Ageism in access to goods and services

- Social network
- Medication management
- Dementia and care

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The screenshot displays the Euro Ageism website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for 'About', 'Consortium', 'Team', 'Research projects', and 'Research training'. A search bar is located on the right side of the header. Below the navigation, the main content area features a section titled 'Meet our Early Stage Researchers'. This section includes four researcher profiles, each with a portrait photo, name, and a brief description of their research focus. Social media icons for LinkedIn, Twitter, and email are provided for each researcher.

Meet our Early Stage Researchers

Researcher Name	Research Focus
Lola Casal-Sanchez	Equality and rights
Hopf, Stefan	A Comparative Evaluation of Equality Legislation
Xi, Wanyu	Increasing Accessibility to Technology
Kim, Seyoung	Ageism, Longevity and the Sustainability of Social Security

Additional visible text on the page includes 'PhD Students', 'Coordinator', and 'Principal Investigators' in the left sidebar, and 'Key texts on ageism', 'News', 'Project outcomes', 'Media', and 'Blog_C' in the top right navigation area.

EuroAgeism Policies briefs

<https://euroageism.eu/>

Funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

Policy Report

Implications for policy and planning to foster solidarity between the generations and enhance healthy life among older adults

Work Pack

Early Stage Researcher
Hanna Brkic, Abodunrin

WP2 Leader: Prof.

WP2 Deputy Lead: Prof.

